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16 April 2024

Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles)

This is being self-declared that Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD student ID: 3820066 has been completed PhD requirement by sole-author PhD research and sole-author PhD publication, supervised by Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain continued his full-time PhD research and his full scholarship period PhD research at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia. Md. Anowar Hossain faced a conspiracy of life-threatening in Melbourne, directed, planned & critically executed by Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was able to present a complete PhD thesis for his confirmation of PhD candidature in 2020-2021. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye also announced 'Nobel Nominee of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University on behalf of Martin G. Bean, Former Vice Chancellor, RMIT University. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain successfully completed the requirements of his PhD (Fashion & Textiles) concentrating on color engineering, camouflage engineering and camouflage textiles. Professor (Dr.) Rajiv Padhye tried to kill PhD candidate and tried to cease the intellectual property of PhD candidate under an official act of hidden life-threatening in Australian PhD school. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain also studied criminology when he defended against the official act of hidden life-threatening at PhD school. The life-threatening history was officially notified to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University and whole concern of RMIT University, whole concern of Australian Community under Australian Quality of Research Framework. The PhD degree was accomplished through non-compliance harassment & motivation such as completing the first milestone & second milestone without revision and negative comments under congratulations and positive comments; the number of action & support-2; hampering PhD progress; verbal threatening & harassment in different way; continuous conspiracy of life-threatening of Md. Anowar Hossain; unethical executive suspension; psychologist bullying of PhD school; PhD school connection with the psychologist; immoral cancellation of PhD enrolment and forwarded to Victorian Ombudsman; Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain reported to the Victorian police station; reported to the National Security of Australia; reported to Australian Institute of Criminology; reported to the Australian Federal Police; reported to country court of Australia; reported to the high court of Australia; reported to The Hon Anthony Albanese MP; Prime Minister of Australia; the life-threatening conspiracy of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain reported to the Victorian State Ministers of Australia in 2023 who are Premier of Victoria, The Hon. Jacinta Allan MP; Deputy Premier of Victoria, The Hon. Ben Carroll MP; Minister for Ambulance Services, The Hon. Mary-Anne Thomas MP; Minister for Crime Prevention & Minister for Police; The Hon. Anthony Carabines

"When moral right is a question mark in a PhD schooling platform, a piece of certificate may fail to judge a right person of a genuine PhD holder," a speech of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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MP; Minister for Education, The Hon. Ben Carroll MP; Minister for Health, The Hon. Mary-Anne Thomas; Minister for Higher Education, The Hon. Gayle Tierney MLC; Minister for Mental Health, Ingrid Stitt MLC; Minister for Victim Support, The Hon. Enver Erdogan MLC; the life-threatening conspiracy reported to Australian Bar association; reported to Australian education department; reported to Tertiary Education Quality & Standards Agency of Australian Government; reported to Australian home affairs; reported to Australian foreign affairs; reported to Victoria legal aid; reported to Australian Competition and Consumer Commission; reported to Australian crime Commission; reported to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Attorney-General or law minister, Attorney-General's Department-Australian Government; reported to education minister, requested and proposed 9450000USD (in words ninety-four lakhs and fifty thousands USD) for income support compensation for life-time duration; requested and proposed 22680000USD (in words two crore twenty-six lakhs and eighty thousands USD) for life-safety compensation for life-time duration; self-invested around 1800000 USD (in words eighteen lakh USD) for his self-sacrifice and self-earning under Australian Compliance, reported to international human rights; different related organizations in Australia. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain was unable to fight with the Australian court due to financial hardship. This whole report was submitted to the Australian Honours and Awards Secretariat; submitted to the office of the Australian high commissioner to Bangladesh; the high commissioner of Bangladesh to Australia; Governor-General of the Commonwealth of Australia, the Honourable David Hurley AC DSC (Retd); submitted to Nobel organization for Nobel nomination about life-threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain. Unfortunately, the life-threatening/conspiracy of killing PhD candidate issue was intentionally converted to the cancellation of material approval for PhD research & PhD progress-2021, executive suspension-2022, psychologist bullying-2023 and cancellation of PhD enrolment-2023. A full scholarship payment was not provided to PhD candidate, a lot of research allowance was not provided to PhD candidate and a lot of time allowance was not provided to PhD candidate. Hence, paid scholarship was around 252666AUD including tuition/professor's fees, the nonpaid PhD scholarship was around 36426AUD and the nonpaid salary was around 249209AUD for artificial financial harassment of research progress at School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University. A copy of this PhD certificate has been forwarded to Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University (vc@rmit.edu.au), school office and all concerned offices at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.

13 April 2024

(Md. Anowar Hossain)

"When moral right is a question mark in a PhD schooling platform, a piece of certificate may fail to judge a right person of a genuine PhD holder," a speech of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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Attached scanned copies of certificates and evidences

Professional Certificates and Professional achievements of Md. Anowar Hossain

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16572.62089>

Academic Certificates, academic achievements and citizen identity of Md. Anowar Hossain.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33349.83689>

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“When moral right is a question mark in a PhD schooling platform, a piece of certificate may fail to judge a right person of a genuine PhD holder,” a speech of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

Cite: Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles); School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; 16 April 2024; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.

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"When moral right is a question mark in a PhD schooling platform, a piece of certificate may fail to judge a right person of a genuine PhD holder," a speech of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist

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- Hossain, M. A. (2023d). *Reporting for psychologist involvement of Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, delegate of Vice Chancellor, RMIT University as per office order of RMIT University, Australia.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.11792.99846>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8330262>
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Reporting to Victoria Legal Aid, Australia for the grant of legal assistance for ethical defending for the peace in PhD education against conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD School.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18289.25443>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10207100>
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

Hossain, M. A. (2023g). *Services for crime protection and crime analysis for the peace of mankind in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Khagan, Birulia, Savar, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36618.03522>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279067>

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<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>

Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Scientist.* a. f. P. e. a. o. t. w. o. J. Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13431.39840>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>

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